

EN 111 – Engineering Practice and Sustainability Greening Engineering

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My Sustainability Action
Dr. Mirzi Betasolo

Article Info

Lecturer: Dr. Mirzi Betasolo
This essay covers SDG numbers 5,6,7, 13 & 16 from the context of Electrical Engineering

Acronyms

PNG – Papua New Guinea
SDG – Sustainable Development Goal

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NATURES PLEA

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Introduction

The literary is a deliverable of the class EN111, Engineering Practice & Sustainability under the class of Dr Mirzi Betasolo of the School of Civil Engineering. The literature contains five Sustainable Development Goals:6,7, 13, 16 & 17

Keywords: Sustainability, Clean Water and Sanitation, Life on Land, Life on Water, Affordable & Clean Energy, Peace Justice & Strong Institutions, Partnership for the Goal

In a world burdened by human hands,
Nature's plea resounds across the lands.
Through whispers of forests, rivers, and skies,
Environmental damage, it sadly implies.

Yearning for a future free of strife,
Sustainable development, our guiding life.
But reckless actions tarnish and mar,
The once vibrant creatures and ecosystems afar.

Agriculture's power, a double-edged blade,
Nourishing nations, yet leaving soil betrayed.
In the pursuit of abundance, we failed to see,
The toll paid by nature's delicate decree.

Beneath the waves, a silenced symphony,
Oceans once vibrant, now filled with agony.
Pollution's deadly sign, a mournful plight,
Stripping harmony, causing eternal fight.

Upon the Earth, treasures lush and grand,
Majestic forests, a sanctuary so grand.
Yet greed's insatiable hunger and desire,
Leaves barren landscapes, a tragedy to admire.

Injustice blooms amidst this harsh scene,
Communities suffer, their voices unseen.
Corrupted power obscures the light,
Of equality and peace, we must strive to ignite.

Let's foster partnerships, steadfast and true,
To forge a resilient world, vibrant and new.
With open hearts and minds, hand in hand,
We shall pave the path, our goals expand.

Interconnectedness binds us all,
Beyond creed, color, or any wall.
Let empathy's flame within us ignite,
Shaping a future where all souls take flight.

United we stand, in harmony we dwell,
Guarding nature, our sacred citadel.
For the future generations, let us comprehend,
That we hold the power, a chance to transcend.

In every choice we make, the path is clear,
To heal the wounds and banish the fear.
Together we rise, hope firmly engraved,
Striving for a world where compassion is saved.

The tapestry of life needs our tender care,
Cultivating harmony, not a moment to spare.
Through mindful choices, let us transcend,
Mending the wounds, a world to mend